
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE STUDY OF TRANSNATIONAL BANKS

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KEYWORDS

banks, transnational banks,
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ABSTRACT

A distinctive feature of banking activity at the present stage is the strengthening of the processes of its transnationalization on a global scale. At the end of the XX century, there was a "blurring" of the boundaries of national economic systems and sharply intensified competition of national technical and economic potentials. These circumstances have led to the initialization of the process of globalization.

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The institutional form of a new level of internationalization of capital and production are transnational corporations. Moreover, a new level of international cooperation and specialization of production is beginning to be determined by the fact that the boundaries of domestic markets are becoming tight for specialized large-scale production. It is TNCs that become new subjects of world economic life, which, firstly, compete for the redistribution of the existing world market, and secondly, form world demand depending on the products they offer. Consequently, TNCs, playing a decisive role in the integration of the economies of developed countries, respectively, can stimulate the strengthening of integration processes in developing countries.

Let's review the literature on the definition of transnational banks. "Multinational banking involves the ownership of banking services in one country by citizens of another country" [Baker and Bradford (1974), Bay (1974), Lees (1974 and 1976) and Robinson (1972)]. The definition of TNB is open to many interpretations and is also used interchangeably with terms such as International Bank or Multinational Bank. In general, a multinational bank can be classified as an institution through correspondent banking, foreign direct investment, or direct lending to customers from home offices that engage in interbank banking. However, in many cases, a multinational bank is used to refer to a bank with a physical presence outside its country of residence, through a branch, agency, wholly or majority-owned subsidiary, or a bank formed by the merger of two or more banks based in different countries, and not those with correspondent relationships or representation. Robinson (1972) defined multinational banking as "the management of a bank and the conduct of banking operations originating in many different countries and national systems". A multinational bank can be compared to a multinational company and can be categorized as a financial multinational corporation as they have similar advantages and disadvantages in the host country. However, this theory can only be applied to a commercial bank that is engaged in local banking activities in the host country and therefore competes with local banks. H. G. Grabel (1977) was one of the first authors to offer a general theory to explain the existence of multinational banking. He argued that there were three different types of TNB that required different explanations.

The first was multinational retail banking that entered overseas markets to serve local customers through the same local deposits and loans as local banks in host countries. The second category was multinational banking, which consisted of banks serving the needs of corporate clients and expatriates from their home country in foreign markets. Finally, multinational wholesale banking involves large deposits, as well as large loans and investments.

It is worth noting that Hoschka's (1993) definition of a multinational financial services corporation (MFSC) is limited to firms that provide banking services. In his opinion, the fact that he owns a representative office in a given country does not mean that the owner of this office can be called a multinational financial services corporation MFSC, since he

simply acts as a liaison function for the parent company, but cannot actively operate in the host country market.

However, the definition the researcher used for a transnational bank refers to any bank that internationalizes its activities. (Jones. D) because he is merely a liaison for the parent company, but cannot be active in the host country market." These are the main approaches to the definition of transnational banks.

Since transnational banks (TNB) act as a kind of transnational corporations (TNCs), it is possible to consider TNB from the side of approaches to defining TNCs. In the scientific literature and periodicals, there are various definitions of a large company, which, in addition to being active in the territory of its registration, also operates outside it. Thus, transnational banks, like transnational corporations, are subjects of the world economy, which carry out their activities through their foreign branches.

A transnational corporation or multinational corporation (MNC) is a corporate entity that owns or controls the production of goods or services in at least one country other than its home country.

Black's Law Dictionary suggests that a company or group be considered a multinational corporation if it derives 25% or more of its income from operations outside the country. A multinational corporation may also be referred to as a multinational enterprise (MNE), multinational enterprise (TNE), multinational corporation (TNC), international corporation, or stateless corporation. There are subtle but real differences between these three labels, and between the multinational corporation and the global enterprise.

References:

1. Akramovich N. A. THE PRIORITY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 10. – C. 185-191.
2. Nizametdinov A., Ahmedova H. Elektron ta'lim metodologiyasi rivojlantirishning usullari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 29-31.
3. Nizametdinov A. A. OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING AGRAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR QO'LLASH USTUVORLIGI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1 (6), 58-60. – 2022.
4. Nizametdinov A. A. OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA AGRAR SOHANING USTUVORLIGI UNDA INNOVATSIYALARNING QULLANISHI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1 (6), 96-98. – 2022.
5. Akramovich N. A. HISTORY, SUBJECT AND OBJECT OF FORMATION OF "MACROECONOMICS" //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 1. – C. 209-210.
6. Мухтаров Б. А. Оптимальное распределение объемов строительно-монтажных работ //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 22. – С. 427-431.

7. Мухтаров Б. А. Имитационная система прогнозирования факторов в легкой промышленности // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – №. 40. – С. 122-124.
8. Мухтаров Б. А., Ортиков Ё. Ю. Культурное и экономическое развитие туризма в Узбекистане // Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 14. – С. 375-378.
9. Muxtarov B., Murotjonova M. O'zbekiston respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik sub 'ektlarining rivojlanishi // Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 581-584.
10. Muxtarov B. Ozbekiston respublikasida axoli daromadlarini osish dinamikasi // Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 579-581.
11. Мухтаров Б. А., Джамалов У. И. ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ КОЛИЧЕСТВО ШКОЛ НА 2022 ГОД ДЛЯ РОССИЙСКОЙ ФЕДЕРАЦИИ // Устойчивое развитие науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 8. – С. 6-11.
12. Abdusattarovich M. B. CALCULATING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN // Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 1189-1194.
13. Ogli R. A. R. THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE CONCEPTS OF DATABASE AND DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM // Archive of Conferences. – 2022. – С. 33-34.
14. Abdukarimov A., Rashidov A. Ma'lumotlar bazalarining–biznesni tashil etish va samaradorligini oshirishdagi roli // Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 132-135.
15. Uchkun Rashidov, Abror Rashidov, & Saidjon Naimov. (2022). Modern Views on the Problems of Management Accounting in Logistics System. "ONLINE - CONFERENCES&Quot; PLATFORM, 276–283. Retrieved from <http://papers.online-conferences.com/index.php/titfl/article/view/937>
16. Uchkun Rashidov, & Abror Rashidov. (2022). Assessment of Costs For the Quality of Logistics Activities. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY, 1(3), 39–43. Retrieved from <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/ijbde/article/view/128>
17. Uchkun Rashidov, & Abror Rashidov. (2022). Assessment of Costs For the Quality of Logistics Activities. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY, 1(3), 39–43. Retrieved from <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/ijbde/article/view/128>
18. Dots. Abdumanap Abdukarimov, & Assist. Abror Rashidov R. (2022). 7 FREE BEST OPEN SOURCE DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 7, 40–47. Retrieved from <https://sjird.journalspark.org/index.php/sjird/article/view/234>

19. Rashidov , A. (2022). IQTISODIYOTNI TARTIBGA SOLISHDA NOTARIF USULLARINING O`RNI VA AHAMIYATI. Архив научных исследований, 2(1). извлечено от <http://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/1016>
20. Rashidov Abror Ro'zimurod o'g'li. (2022). JIZZAX VILOYATI IQTISODIY O'SISH KO'RSATKICHLARI YOKI JARAYONLARI . PEDAGOGS Jurnal, 5(1), 20–22. Retrieved from <http://www.pedagoglar.uz/index.php/ped/article/view/290>
21. Рашидов У., Рашидов А. Iqtisodiyotni tartibga solishda notarif usullarining ornı va ahamiyati //Вопросы усиления позиций Узбекистана в международной торговле и оптимизации его интеграции в мировой рынок в условиях глобальной трансформации. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 53-58.
22. Ismailova N. S. et al. JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA QO'SHILISH: QO'SHILISH JARAYONI HAMDA UNING QONUNIY ASOSLARI //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 1095-1098.
23. Xaydarov, B., & Saitov, S. (2022). Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari. Zamonaviy Innovatsion Tadqiqotlarning Dolzarb Muammolari Va Rivojlanish Tendensiyalari: Yechimlar Va Istiqbollar, 1(1), 634–635. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5390>
24. Бахром Х. Х. БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 2. – С. 139-142.
25. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA HORIJIIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 151-156.
26. Хайдаров Б. ИҚТISODIЙ ИСЛОХОТЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА КАМБАҒАЛЛИКНИ ҚISҚАРТИРИШ //Экономика и образование. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 288-292.
27. To'yuchiyeva N. Elektron Ta 'lim Tizimining Afzalliklari Va Kamchiliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 40-41.
28. Норбеков Х., Туйчиева Н. Формирование конкурентных преимуществ компании //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 589-592.
29. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PRONUNCIATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN SCHOOL STUDENTS //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
30. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION TO PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS IS BASED ON THE JAPANESE EXPERIENCE //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 205-208.
31. Nodira T., Rashid X. PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 155-164.

32. Nodira T. PRIORITIES FOR ORGANIZING ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 192-199.
33. Nodira T. INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 346-351.
34. To'ychiyeva, N. (2022). AGRAR SOHADA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(4), 53–56. Retrieved from <http://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/625>
35. To'ychiyeva, N. (2022). AGRAR TARMOQDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY ASOSLARI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(4), 3–6. Retrieved from <http://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/624>
36. To'ychiyeva N. THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 103-105.
37. Nodira T., Maxfirat T. FOREIGN LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION IN GRADES 1-4» //РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ. – С. 1133.
38. Хосилмуродов И. О 'zbekistonda bag 'rikenglik va millatlararo totuvlik g 'oyalarining ijtimoiy hayotdagi ahamiyati //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11/S. – С. 16-24.
39. Хосилмуродов И., Султоналиева Г. Тафаккур услубининг фалсафий-методологик тахлили //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 549-551.
40. Арзикулов О. А. Значение малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в узбекистана //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 157-160.
41. Maksimov Y. V. et al. The integrating role of systems engineer in oil and gas projects (Russian) //Neftyanoe khozyaystvo-Oil Industry. – 2019. – Т. 2019. – №. 12. – С. 12-15.
42. Arzikulov O. A. THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES //Экономика и социум. – 2019. – №. 12. – С. 30-33.
43. Arzikulov O. UY XO'JALIKLARINING DAROMAD MANBALARI VA ISTE'MOL XARAJATLARINI STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLARINI O'RGANISH //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.
44. Ali o'g'li A. O. STATISTICAL STUDY OF DIRECT MAINTENANCE OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITIES IN THE REGIONS //EPRA International Journal of Economic and Business Review (JEER). – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 6. – С. 30-33.
45. Arzikulov O. Iqtisodiyotni liberallashtirish sharoitida kichik korxonalarda innovatsion jarayonlar //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.

46. To'ychiyeva, Nodira. "Elektron Ta'lim Tizimining Afzalliklari Va Kamchiliklari." *Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar 1.1* (2022): 40-41.
47. Норбеков, Хурсандмурод, and Нодира Туйчиева. "Формирование конкурентных преимуществ компании." *Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar 1.1* (2022): 589-592.
48. Jamshidovna B. M., Bahodirovich F. S. Innovative methods and techniques in the education system //current research journal of pedagogics. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 147-151.
49. Fayzullaev S. B. Fostering the qualities of agility of basketball pupils in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 5. – С. 1171-1176.
50. Fayzullaeva D. N. et al. Dialectisms used in dastan "Alpamish" //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (80). – 2019. – С. 469-472.
51. Nasirov B. U., Boltaeva M. J. Genesis And Transformation Of The Public Catering System In Uzbekistan During The Soviet Period //Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI) Volume. – Т. 12. – С. 5834-5841.
52. Nasirov B. Catering In Uzbekistan From The History Of The System //The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations Research. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 11-15.
53. Насиров Б. XX АСРНИНГ 30-80 ЙИЛЛАРИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА УМУМИЙ ОВҚАТЛАНИШ ТИЗИМИ ТАРИХИДАН //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 1.
54. Носиров Б., Носирова Ф. Ўзбекистонда умумий овқатланиш тизимининг шаклланиши ва унга аҳоли эҳтиёжининг ортиб бориши (совет ҳукумати йилларида) //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2020. – Т. 3. – №. 3.
55. Носиров Б. Совет даврида Ўзбекистонда умумий овқатланиш тизими фаолияти хусусида //Взгляд в прошлое. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4.
56. Насыров Б. У. История деятельности бань в восточных странах //International scientific review. – 2016. – №. 4 (14). – С. 62-66.
57. Носиров Б., Носирова Ф. СИСТЕМА БЫТОВОГО ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ: ГЕНЕЗИС И ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРАКТИКИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН В 60-80 ГОДЫ ПРОШЛОГО ВЕКА) //Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2017. – №. 1-4. – С. 41-46.
58. Nasirov B. HISTORICAL SCIENCES //Главный редактор научно-исследовательского журнала «International scientific review», Вальцев СВ. – 2016. – №. 4. – С. 61.
59. Носиров Б. Механизмы и противоречивое развитие сферы бытового обслуживания в Узбекистане 20-40 годах XX века //Культура. Духовность. Общество. – 2014. – №. 11. – С. 158-163.

60. Uralovich N. B. TRANSFORMATIONAL PROCESSES IN THE GENERAL FOOD SYSTEM (in the example of the catering system in the late 19th and early 20th centuries) //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 1253-1258.

61. Носиров Б. ИЖТИМОЙИ-МАИШИЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРАЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ЭЪТИБОРГА ОЛИНМАГАН ОМИЛЛАР (СОВЕТ ДАВРИДА): Носиров Бунёд, Тарих фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори, доцент. Мирзо Улуғбек номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий университети Жиззах филиали //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 8-12.

62. Musaev O. et al. The role of public control in improving the system of public administration //Solid State Technology. – 2020. – Т. 63. – №. 6. – С. 96-104.

63. E'tiborxon Mallaeva S. M. МАФКУРА ВА МАФКУРАВИЙ КАТЕГОРИЯЛАР ЎРТАСИДАГИ ЎЗАРО МУНОСАБАТНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ЖИ //АТЛАРИ, Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.

64. E'tiborxon Mallaeva M. иллик ва миллий-маънавий? адриятларнинг тикланиши //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.

65. Маллаева Э. Збекистонда диний бағрикенглик ва миллатлараро муносабатлар масалалари //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 573-576.

66. Fedotova M. A., Tarasova V. N., Mallaeva E. M. Factors and Conditions of Effective Dynamic Innovative Development of Aviation Industry Enterprises //Proceedings of the International Conference Engineering Innovations and Sustainable Development. – Springer, Cham, 2022. – С. 309-318.

67. Маллаева Э. APPROACHES AND ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF POLITICAL CULTURE //Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.

68. Маллаева Э. М. ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ГРАЖДАН НА ОСНОВЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИДЕИ //ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ. – 2019. – С. 31-34.

69. МАЛЛАЕВА Э. М. ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ И НАУЧНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ //Вопросы политологии. – 2019. – Т. 9. – №. 8. – С. 1722-1729.

70. Маллаева Э. Jamiyatning demokratlashuvi-fuqarolar siyosiy madaniyatini rivojlantirish omili sifatida //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11/S. – С. 287-291.

71. Mallaeva E. Les enfants réfugiés de la révolution hongroise de 1956 en Yougoslavie: entre tensions géopolitiques et efforts de coopération humanitaire. – 2020.

72. Xaydarov B., Saitov S. Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 634-635.

73. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – С. 151-156.

74. Bozorboevich R. K. The Ethnic Structure of the Population of the Bukhara Emirate //International Journal on Integrated Education. – T. 4. – №. 12. – С. 8-12.

75. Рахматов Х. Б. БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИ АҲОЛИСИНИНГ ЭТНИК ТАРКИБИ ХУСУСИДА (XIX асрнинг иккинчи ярми–XX аср бошлари) //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2021. – №. SI-3.

76. Рахматов Х. Б. Об Этнической Структуре Населения Бухарского Эмирата //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. – 2021. – T. 2. – С. 273-278.

77. Bozorboevich R. K. The Ethnic Structure of the Population of the Bukhara Emirate //International Journal on Integrated Education. – T. 4. – №. 12. – С. 8-12.

78. Рахматов Х., Набиев Ш. XIX асрнинг сўнги чораги–XX аср бошларида бухоро воҳаси сиёсий-маъмурий бирликлари ва аҳолиси хусусида //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 605-608.

79. Bozorboevich R. K. POLITICAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE STRUCTURE OF THE EMIRATE OF BUKHARA IN THE LATE XIX AND EARLY XX CENTURIES ON THE POPULATION AND ETHNOTOPONYMS //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF HISTORY (2767-472X). – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 04. – С. 48-54.

80. Bozorboevich R. K. ON THE POPULATION AND ETHNIC PROCESSES OF THE POLITICAL-ADMINISTRATIVE UNITS OF THE MIDDLE BASIN OF THE AMUDARYA IN THE LAST QUARTER OF THE 19TH CENTURY AND THE BEGINNING OF THE 20TH CENTURY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 5. – С. 77-85.

81. Рахматов Х. Б. БУХОРО АМИРЛИГИ АҲОЛИСИНИНГ ЭТНИК ТАРКИБИ ХУСУСИДА (XIX асрнинг иккинчи ярми–XX аср бошлари) //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2021. – №. SI-3.

82. Xaydarov B., Saitov S. Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – С. 634-635.

83. Бахром Х. Х. БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 2. – С. 139-142.

84. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – С. 151-156.

85. Хайдаров Б. ИҚТИСОДИЙ ИСЛОҲОТЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА КАМБАҒАЛЛИКНИ ҚИСҚАРТИРИШ //Экономика и образование. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 288-292.
86. G'aybullayev Sarvar O. et al. O 'ZBEKISTONDA ISTE'MOL SAVATCHASI HOZIRGI HOLATINI VA UNI SHAKILLANTIRISH YO 'NALISHLARI //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 119-125.
87. Xudayarov R., Akhror A. BIG DATA TYPES OF EDUCATION SYSTEM AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR USING THEM IN THE FIELD //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.
88. Nodira T., Rashid X. PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 155-164.
89. Khudoyarov R. IMPROVING ECONOMIC GOVERNANCE IN A MARKET ECONOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 610-612.
90. Хакимов О. М., Курбанов З. Х., Мухаммедов Ф. Реализация возможностей получения легких наполнителей на основе меньше пластиковых почв в нашей республике //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 176-181.
91. Khakimov O. M. Issiq-quruq iqlim sharoiti uchun asfaltbeton tarkibini tanlash //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 241-247.
92. Хакимов О., Курбанов З. ПЛАСТИКЛИГИ КАМ ТУПРОҚЛАР АСОСИДА ЕНГИЛ ТЎЛДИРУВЧИЛАР ОЛИШ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИНИ ЎРГАНИШ //Solution of social problems in management and economy. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 58-64.
93. Azimov Y. N. et al. Olympism and olympic education at the present stage //Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в современном мире. – 2016. – №. 13-4. – С. 119-121.
94. Azimov Yusufjon. (2022). DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS, 3(03), 5-8. <https://doi.org/10.37547/pedagogics-crjp-03-03-02>
95. Abror Ro'zimurod o'g R. et al. O 'ZBEKISTONDA PUL-KREDIT TIZIMI VA UNI MODERNIZATSIYALASH YO 'LLARI //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 13. – С. 251-258.
96. Khidirov K. I. et al. Military management and army structure of Sheybanids //The Fourth International conference on development of historical and political sciences in Eurasia. – 2015. – С. 8-11.
97. Ortikov O. K. et al. Views of eastern thinkers on the development of intellectual abilities in the scientific heritage //ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 211-214.

98. Boltaeva M. J., Kh O. Ortikov. Features of the scientific heritage of eastern thinkers about the attitude of parents to the child //Society and innovations. Special. – 2021. – №. 2. – С. 469-474.